

Table S1. Hypotheses considered for explaining species dominance and mixed-effects model comparison. The response variable in our models was ‘EIV’, whereas the explanatory variables consisted of ‘Species’, ‘Condition’, and ‘Time’. In addition, we treated ‘Plot’ as random effects (~1|Site/Plot) and used an autocorrelation-moving average to account for autocorrelation between inventory years. The model incorporating the interaction of ‘Time’ with ‘Species’ had the best fit (lowest AIC) among the seven mixed effects models examined.

Model	Fixed effects	Description	AIC	BIC	Test	p-value
<i>Biological legacies hypothesis</i>						
1	~ Species	The abundance of species may determine the species' dominance	25274	25351		
<i>Spatial hypotheses</i>						
2	~ Site	The burned and the unburned sites are likely to be different after the fire	25752	25787	1 vs 2	<.0001
3	~ Site + Species	Species abundance and the site are likely to affect the species' dominance	25268	25351	2 vs 3	<.0001
4	~ Site * Species	Because of the differences in the conditions between burned and unburned sites, the effect of species abundance on the species' dominance may vary between sites	25234	25364	3 vs 4	<.0001
<i>Temporal hypotheses</i>						
5	~ Time	Time since fire may affect species' dominance	25757	25810	4 vs 5	<.0001
6	~ Time + Species	Species abundance and time since fire affect the species' dominance	25272	25372	5 vs 6	<.0001
7	~Time * Species	Because of variation in time-dependent conditions, species abundance effect on the species' dominance may vary with time since fire	25185	25474	6 vs 7	<.0001

Table S2. Pearson correlation coefficients for nineteen forest structural variables with the two NMDS ordination axes. EIV: Ecological Importance Value; TPH: Trees per Hectare; BAPH: Basal Area per Hectare; CWD: Coarse Woody Debris; FWD: Fine Woody Debris. Species codes are those in Table 1. NMDS1 had a very strong negative correlation with plot tree density and positive correlations with FWD, and Litter, while NMDS2 had a strong positive correlation with *Q.eduardii* EIV.

Variable	MDS1	MDS2
EIV _{ARAR}	-0.0808	-0.02123
EIV _{JUDE}	0.092788	0.500263
EIV _{PIAR}	-0.08994	0.004894
EIV _{PICE}	0.023008	0.07115
EIV _{PIEN}	0.187347	-0.2745
EIV _{PILE}	0.308856	0.161505
EIV _{PITE}	0.068875	-0.31793
EIV _{QUED}	0.084411	-0.62613
EIV _{QUHA}	0.170162	0.478997
TPH	-0.95877	0.01454
BAPH	0.025422	0.109844
FWD	0.648447	-0.08752
CWD	0.227497	-0.01664
Litter	0.612404	0.0203
Duff	0.446465	-0.10381
GSI	0.105592	-0.07354
FS	0.282693	0.441833
OR	0.201142	-0.14699
OS	0.191432	-0.40636

Table S3. P-values for pairwise PERMANOVA analysis (Permutational Multivariate Analysis of Variance) with Bonferroni adjustment method and 999 permutations between sites (burned; unburned) and inventory years.

		burned					unburned			
		1996	1997	2001	2006	2017	1996	1997	2001	2006
burned	1997	0.045	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2001	0.045	0.045	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2006	0.765	0.045	0.045	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2017	0.045	0.045	0.045	1	-	-	-	-	-
unburned	1996	1	0.045	0.225	0.045	0.045	-	-	-	-
	1997	1	0.045	0.225	0.090	0.045	1	-	-	-
	2001	1	0.045	0.18	0.045	0.045	1	1	-	-
	2006	1	0.045	0.18	0.045	0.045	1	1	1	-
	2017	1	0.045	0.99	0.09	0.045	1	1	1	1

Figure S1. Tree density by taxa, diameter class and inventory year and site (burned; unburned)

Figure S2. Tree stump density by family, and site (burned; unburned). Tree stump density, calculated by subtracting the previous inventory stump density per hectare. In cases where stump density per hectare was higher in the previous inventory, the stump density for the inventory was

estimated as zero to reflect no new stumps. The vertical dashed red line represents the fire event. The burned site experienced higher tree harvesting up to a decade after the fire.

Figure S3. Forest(a) fuel loads and (b) floor depth by inventory year and site (burned; unburned). CWD: Coarse Woody Debris; FWD: Fine Woody Debris. Forest floor fuel loads and depth were relatively low and similar between sites and inventory years.

Figure S4. Species ecological importance value (EIV) for the burned site. Boxes show median, 25 %, and 75 % percentiles. Box whiskers and circles show the 10–90 % and 5–95 % percentiles, respectively. The vertical dashed red line represents the fire event. When two means share at least one common letter, there are no significant differences (p -value >0.05) according to Tukey post hoc test. Species codes are those in Table 1. Tukey’s HSD showed significant decrease in the ecological importance value of *Q.eduardii* and *Q.hartwegii* after the fire but regained it five years post fire.